

THE EFFECT OF HEAT STRESS ON PEROXIDASE ACTIVITY AND COTTON MORPHOLOGY

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Annotation: High-temperature stress is a major abiotic factor that adversely affects plant growth and development, particularly in cotton (*Gossypium* spp.). This study aimed to investigate the impact of heat stress (45°C for 6 hours) on peroxidase enzyme activity and morphological traits in two cotton cultivars: Surkhan-103 (conventionally bred) and Ravnaq-1 (developed through marker-assisted selection). The results demonstrated a significant increase (27.7%) in peroxidase activity in the heat-tolerant Surkhan-103 cultivar, while a sharp decline (40%) was observed in the Ravnaq-1 cultivar, indicating its susceptibility to elevated temperatures. Morphological analyses further confirmed these differences, with Surkhan-103 maintaining growth parameters under stress, while Ravnaq-1 exhibited reductions in plant height, root length, and biomass. These findings highlight the physiological and biochemical basis of heat tolerance in cotton and provide valuable information for breeding programs targeting climate-resilient cultivars.

Keywords: heat stress, *Gossypium hirsutum*, peroxidase activity, morphological traits, marker-assisted selection.

Annotatsiya: Yuqori haroratli stress o'simliklarning o'sishi va rivojlanishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadigan asosiy abiotik omillardan biridir. Ushbu tadqiqot 45°C haroratda 6 soat davomida issiqlik stressi sharoitida ikkita paxta (*Gossypium* spp.) navida — an'anaviy seleksiya asosida yaratilgan Surxon-103 va markerlarga asoslangan seleksiya (MAS) orqali olingan Ravnaq-1 navlarida peroksidaza fermenti faolligi hamda morfologik o'zgarishlarni baholashga qaratildi. Natijalar Surxon-103 navida peroksidaza faolligi nazoratga nisbatan 27,7% ga oshganini ko'rsatdi, Ravnaq-1 navida esa bu ferment faolligi 40% ga kamaydi. Bu Ravnaq-1 navining yuqori haroratga nisbatan sezuvchanligini ko'rsatadi. Morfologik ko'rsatkichlar ham bu farqni tasdiqladi: Surxon-103 navi issiqlik sharoitida o'sish parametrlarini saqlab qolgan bo'lsa, Ravnaq-1 navida o'simlik bo'yi, ildiz uzunligi va biomassasi sezilarli darajada pasaydi. Ushbu natijalar paxta navlarining issiqlik stressiga chidamliligini baholash va mos navlarni tanlashda muhim ilmiy asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: issiqlik stressi, *Gossypium hirsutum*, peroksidaza faolligi, morfologik ko'rsatkichlar, markerlarga asoslangan seleksiya.

Аннотация: Высокотемпературный стресс является одним из основных абиотических факторов, негативно влияющих на рост и развитие растений, особенно у хлопчатника (*Gossypium* spp.). В настоящем исследовании изучались активность пероксидазы и морфологические изменения у двух сортов хлопчатника при температуре 45°C в течение 6 часов: Сурхон-103 (созданный методами классической селекции) и Равнак-1 (полученный с применением маркер-ассоциированной селекции). Полученные данные показали, что у сорта

Сурхон-103 активност пероксидазы увеличилась на 27,7% по сравнению с контролем, тогда как у Равнак-1 она снизилась на 40%, что свидетельствует о его чувствительности к высокотемпературному стрессу. Морфологический анализ подтвердил эти различия: Сурхон-103 сохранял основные параметры роста, в то время как у Равнак-1 наблюдалось значительное снижение высоты растения, длины корней и биомассы. Эти результаты подчеркивают значение физиологических и биохимических показателей для оценки устойчивости сортов хлопчатника к жароустойчивости и их дальнейшего использования в селекционных программах.

Ключевое слово: тепловой стресс, *Gossypium hirsutum*, активност пероксидазы, морфологические показатели, маркер-ассоциированная селекция.

High temperatures have a detrimental effect on plant growth and metabolism, as each plant species has an optimal temperature range for these physiological processes [1]. Currently, heat is considered one of the major abiotic stress factors limiting crop production [2]. In particular, heat stress significantly affects the physiological activity of cotton. Elevated temperatures disrupt various physiological processes, including water exchange, photosynthesis, transpiration, stomatal regulation, enzyme function, hormonal balance, and antioxidant defense mechanisms [3]. The aim of this study was to analyze peroxidase enzyme activity and morphological changes in cotton cultivars under high-temperature stress.

Two cotton cultivars were used in the study. One was Ravnaq-1, developed through marker-assisted selection and provided by the Center for Genomics and Bioinformatics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The other cultivar, Surkhan-103 from the *Gossypium barbadense* species, was developed through conventional breeding and obtained from the Research Institute of Cotton Breeding, Seed Production, and Agrotechnology's under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Seeds were germinated in darkness at 30°C for 7 days. To simulate hyperthermia stress, the seedlings were exposed to a temperature of 45°C for 6 hours.

The results revealed an increase in peroxidase activity in the Surkhan-103 cultivar under 45°C heat stress, whereas this response was not observed in the Ravnaq-1 cultivar developed via MAS technology (Fig.1). Specifically, Surkhan-103 exhibited a 27.7% increase in peroxidase activity compared to the control. In contrast, Ravnaq-1 showed the lowest peroxidase activity under heat stress, with a 40% reduction relative to its control. These findings suggest that Ravnaq-1 is highly sensitive to elevated temperatures, as indicated by the significant decline in peroxidase levels (Fig.1).

Figure 1. The effect of 6-hour heat stress at 45°C on peroxidase activity and morphological traits in two different cotton cultivars

In addition to enzymatic changes, high temperatures also markedly affected the morpho-physiological characteristics of the tested cultivars (Fig.1). Experimental data indicated that Surkhan-103 and Ravnak-1 exhibited contrasting morphological responses to high-temperature stress (45°C). Surkhan-103 appeared to be relatively heat-tolerant, with no significant alterations in morphological traits such as plant height, root length, or biomass (Fig.1). The plants maintained their structural integrity and growth capacity under stress, indicating the presence of inherent physiological adaptation mechanisms.

Conversely, Ravnak-1 displayed a pronounced sensitivity to elevated temperatures, with evident morphological impairments (Fig.1). Plant height was reduced, likely due to impaired cellular water balance, which in turn limits cell expansion and vegetative growth. Root development was also adversely affected, as root elongation slowed and biomass decreased under heat stress, negatively impacting water and nutrient uptake. Leaf morphology changed significantly: leaf size was reduced, and leaf margins often curled or wilted. These symptoms are indicative of increased transpiration and water loss, leading to dehydration stress.

The distinct responses of Surkhan-103 and Ravnak-1 to high-temperature conditions clearly demonstrate their differential tolerance to heat stress. These results provide valuable insights for future cotton breeding and agronomic management practices aimed at improving heat resilience in cotton.

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